

Eurodoc Gender Equality and Anti-Discrimination Plan

Introduction

Gender Equality, Equality, and Anti-Discrimination as the core of Eurodoc's mission and vision

Eurodoc vision is that of “a fair and sustainable research culture where early career researchers are treated with respect and have access to long-term and stable career pathways”, and its mission is that of advocating “for positive change in the policies, culture and environment that affect the quality of training, well-being and employment conditions of early career researchers”. For this very reason, gender inequalities, along with any other inequality and discrimination on whatever basis are phenomena Eurodoc must fight against.

The document is structured as follows. Section 2 focuses on the current state of affairs, and provides an overview of the organisational structure including the position of trust of Eurodoc as well as the European equality projects that Eurodoc participates in. Section 3 focuses on challenges that Eurodoc faces when it comes to ensuring equal opportunities, its vision on the topic as well as the suggested commitments of Eurodoc for 2023/2024.

The background for this document

In its 21-years long story, Eurodoc has always had the real people at its core, and this is where its strength as an advocate stems from. For most Eurodoc volunteers, the “Eurodocers”, our organisation has been a place where one could find moral support in the difficulties of the PhD journey, mutual help in the development of tasks, fair collaboration for the achievement of common goals, and even personal career development opportunities. Eurodoc culture was set from the beginning on mutual respect and mutual valorisation of each other's capabilities, skills and aspirations. This document, Eurodoc's Gender Equality, Equality, and Anti Discrimination Plan (GEP) initiated by the 2021/2022 Board should be seen as following this tradition.

The 2021/2022 Board had a strong focus on ensuring equal opportunities within Eurodoc and to work on an European level to ensure equal opportunities for Early Career Researchers (ECRs). This led to the 2021/2022 Board introducing National Association meetings, proposing the development of a GEP, and beside the creation of the role of a Gender Equality Officer in Eurodoc. The creation of a “Gender Equality Officer” (GEO)¹ is meant to advance the work on gender equality both outside and inside our organisation. Among the GEO's tasks was to lead the development of the aforementioned GEP.

¹ In the term 2022/2023 this officer was called Gender Equality Officer, for the term 2023/2024 it will be renamed Equality Officer emphasising that equal opportunities entails more than gender equality.

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An analysis of Eurodoc's core on the equality organisational culture and European engagement

In this section an analysis of the current status of Eurodoc's work and commitment towards ensuring equal opportunities is analysed. The first part concerns the internal work of Eurodoc and focus on the following five pillars

- Gender distribution of position of trust
- Recruitment processes of volunteers and recognition of volunteers contributions
- Work-life balance
- Measures towards preventing gender based violence

These four pillars have been identified as crucial on the basis of the Toolkit "Gender Equality in Academia" developed by the European Institution for Gender Equality and to ensure the continuation of the traditional open and welcoming organisational culture of Eurodoc, which is foundation of the organisational culture we want to strengthen inside and outside Eurodoc.

On this basis, we aim to adopt the GEP methodology to tackle also other forms of discrimination.

This analysis is then followed by a short overview of the Eurodoc's engagement in Equal Opportunities on a European level.

Position of trust and election procedures.

Gender distribution of the position of trust

In the domain of **position of trust**, our sex disaggregated data show that in the last 5 years Eurodoc has had a good gender balance with a slight majority of women in positions of trust. In the last years its Boards have usually consisted more women than men². The same is true for the Secretariat, however here the majority of women in the current administration is cause for reflections³.

Recruitment procedures and recognition of volunteers' contributions

The requirements for positions of trust in Eurodoc are very simple. Except for positions in the board, which require an affiliation with a National Association, all positions have no

² The 2018-2019 Board counted 4 men and 3 women, the 2019-2020 Board 3 men and 5 women, the 2021-2021 Board 3 men and 4 women, the 2021-2022 Board 2 men and 5 women, the 2022-2023 Board 3 men and 4 women. Data is available on the Eurodoc website.

³ The 2018-2019 Secretariat counted 13 men and 14 women, the 2019-2020 Secretariat 10 men and 16 women, the 2020-2021 Secretariat 6 men and 18 women, the 2021-2022 Secretariat 7 men and 12 women, the 2022-2023 Secretariat 4 men and 12 women. Data is available on the Eurodoc website.

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formal requirements. Eurodoc Working Groups (WGs) are open for any early career researcher, and support individuals to get in touch with National Associations (NAs) members of Eurodoc. Similarly, the Eurodoc administration actively encourages NAs to propose their members to join Eurodoc activities and to candidate them for positions of trust.

In encouraging individuals to step up for positions, the Eurodoc administration highlights that thanks to a traditionally open and welcoming organisational culture, becoming an Eurodoccer is an extraordinary opportunity for people who experience discrimination in the workplace to link their personal experience with widespread issues and to contribute to change through policy making. Volunteers can also have the chance to take on responsibility and leadership roles in a supporting environment, developing transferable skills that will strengthen their career development opportunities. We believe that to stress this point makes Eurodoc able to encourage women and people who experience(d) marginalisation to be included in our team.

At the same time, for Eurodoc to continue to perform this task with full awareness, it is necessary that Eurodoccers are openly recognized for their contributions. Credit where credit is due is an important component of Open Science, and how to recognize these contributions has been a focus of Eurodoc for several years. The 2022-2023 administration has implemented clear procedures for authorship and other contributions, as well as a standard of issuing diplomas for participation in conferences, presentations, and for serving in positions of trust. While it should be recognized that this is a huge step in the right direction, it should also be mentioned that these practices can be strengthened by being written into a code of conduct for Eurodoc.

Work-life balance

A domain where Eurodoc potentially can have large shortcomings is that of ensuring **work-life balance**. In general, ECRs' worklife is pervaded by a narrative that praises overworking, and volunteer activity can sometimes implicate an attitude of self-sacrifice. Since Eurodoc is a volunteer organisation of ECRs, to be aware of these stereotypes and correct the organisational culture on this aspect is challenging. However, the current emphasis that the 2022-2023 and 2021-2022 Boards have had on that Eurodoc's organisational culture must have a special focus on not sustaining the unhealthy habits and values of academia is an important step in the right direction. However strong this current focus is, it is based on practices and the beliefs of the current board, and could be strengthened by being specified in a code of conduct.

Gender-based violence

Reducing gender-based violence is an important topic and identifying measures to prevent such is an crucial part of a GEP. To this, we want to add our commitment to prevent violent behaviours against any person, including those coming from marginalised categories.

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While Eurodoc aims at providing a safe environment where any type of gender-based violence, including sexual violence or harassment, is unacceptable whether it happens at internal Eurodoc meetings or at external meetings representing Eurodoc. However, as also noted above, the lack of a code of conduct leaves the organisation without ways of systematically surveying the situation and without a transparent process for reporting issues. At the same time, we believe that Eurodoc can strengthen its ability to prevent and recognise gender-based violence and violence against marginalised groups through internal training, that should be mandatory for all people in positions of trust and open for NAs delegates.

Eurodoc's commitments in 2023/2024.

Starting from this first analysis, Eurodoc commits itself for the term 2023/2024 to take the following concrete measures:

- To develop a code of conduct for Eurodoc's internal work as well as external representation.
 - The work should be led by Equality Officer and the board
- To develop a formal training of the new administration on equality issues.
 - This work should be led by the Equality Officer and the board.

As mandated by the GEP basic requirements, these measures will be evaluated and reviewed with a regular participatory process during the second half of next term. On this basis, a new analysis and a new round of concrete measures will be presented to the 2024 AGM for approval.

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Eurodoc, the European Council of Doctoral Candidates and Junior Researchers, is a grassroots federation of 25 national associations of early-career researchers (ECRs) from 23 countries across Europe. Eurodoc was established in 2002 and is based in Brussels. As a representative of doctoral candidates and junior researchers at the European level, Eurodoc engages with all major stakeholders in research and innovation in Europe.

